

Association of Herpesviridae reactivation and SARS-CoV-2 infection or vaccination.

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Abstract

Several authors have published papers reporting of cases of reactivation of Herpes Zoster virus following either infection with SARS-CoV-2 or the CoViD-19 vaccine. Co-infection of SARS-CoV-2 and cytomegalovirus and Epstein-Barr Virus has been reported, associated with poor outcomes. Evidence will be presented that is suggestive of a possible role for the reactivation of herpes viruses associated with post CoViD-19 sequelae or adverse events following vaccination. There appears to be a link between cytokine expression and the reactivation of the different herpes viruses, which is explored by examining the reported evidence from astronauts returning from space. Although published evidence is suggestive of a role for reactivated herpes family in observed signs and symptoms associated with acute SARS-CoV-2 infection, post acute Covid19 sequelae and post vaccination adverse events, further work is necessary including specific testing for the presence of recently active herpes virus family members.

Introduction

Aspects of the presentation of CoViD-19 appear to be similar to signs and symptoms associated with infection with the Human Herpes Virus (HHV) family. Likewise, some of the reported adverse events associated with the different vaccines have signs and symptoms that appear to be indistinguishable from those connected to HHV infection or reactivation. It is important to realise that although there are similarities not every presentation of CoViD-19 or post vaccination sequelae are due to HHV. Also the pathogenesis of HHV reactivation is not fully understood, thus caution is required in the interpretation of the information expressed herein and further work is required.

Structure

The document will begin by with a brief review of relevant elements of the immune system and diseases where herpes viruses are known to be involved and others where there is evidence of their involvement. Following this there will be an examination of herpes virus reactivation, which viruses, the circumstances that led to the reactivation and any associated changes in the immune system that occurred. Finally there will be a discussion on the reports of herpes reactivation during SARS-CoV-2 infection or following vaccination. Tables summarising published material and their findings are included in the appendix.

Immune System review

This section provides an overview of the parts of the immune system that are relevant to this discussion.

Cytokines are chemical messengers that are responsible for the effects of the immune system, these are divided into two functional groups, one that causes the inflammatory response and one that is anti-inflammatory but promotes allergic responses.

T cells, which are the major source of cytokines, consist of two sets that differ by the molecules expressed on their surface called CD4 and CD8.

CD4+ cells are known as helper T (Th) cells.

Th cells can be further divided into two classes known as Th1 and Th2, with the cytokines produced by each class being tagged Th1-type and Th2-type respectively.

Th1 cytokines tend to generate proinflammatory responses against intracellular parasites and for continuing autoimmune responses, thus promoting cellular immunity (Elenkov and Chrousos 2002) by activating natural killer cells, cytotoxic T cells and macrophages.

Cytokines IFN- γ , IL-2 and TNF- β also inhibit the Th-2 response.

Whereas the Th2 cytokines IL-4, IL-10 and IL-13 inhibit the Th-1 response, whilst stimulating humoral immunity involving the maturation of B cells, transforming to become antibody producing, mast cells and eosinophils (Elenkov and Chrousos 2002). Thus a healthy immune system consists of a balanced Th1 and Th2 response proportional to the challenge to the immune system (Berger 2000, Muraille & Leo 1998). The following table is a brief summary of the two different classes of cytokines.

Table 1: Class dependent cytokines

Th-1 Cytokines	Th-2 Cytokines
Interleuken 1 (IL-1)	Interleuken 5 (IL-5)
Interleuken 2 (IL-2)	Interleuken 10 (IL-10)
Interleuken 3 (IL-3)	
Interleuken 12 (IL-12)	Interleuken 13 (IL-13)
Interleuken 6 (IL-6)	Interleuken 22 (IL-22)
Interleuken 11 (IL-11)	Interleuken 37 (IL-37)
Interleuken 17 (IL-17)	Interleuken 38 (IL-38)
Interleuken 18 (IL-18)	Interleuken 4 (IL-4)
Interferon α (IFN- α)	Interleuken 8 (IL-8)
Interferon β (IFN- β)	
Interferon γ (IFN- γ)	
Tumour Necrosis Factor α (TNF- α)	Transforming Growth Factor β (TGF- β)
Tumour Necrosis Factor β (TNF- β)	

Functions of Th1 & Th2 cytokines

Th1 cytokines		Th2 cytokines	
IFN- γ	Enhances the microbicidal function of macrophages. Promotes the differentiation of naive helper T cells into Th1 cells. Activates polymorphonuclear leukocytes, cytotoxic T cells, and NK cells.	IL-4	Regulates antibody production, haematopoiesis, and inflammation. Promotes the differentiation of naive helper T cells into Th2 cells. Decreases the production of Th1 cells.
IL-2	Promotes clonal expansion and development of T and B-lymphocytes. Induces expression of adhesion molecules. Enhances the function of NK cells.	IL-10	Inhibits synthesis of Th1 cytokines such as IFN- γ and IL-2. Inhibits antigen-presenting cells.
IL-15	Induces activation and cytotoxicity of NK cells. Activates macrophages. Promotes proliferation and survival of T and B-lymphocytes and NK cells.	IL-8	Promotes neutrophils chemotaxis and degranulation. Promotes tumour angiogenesis.
IL-21	Regulates proliferation and differentiation of T cells, B cells, and NK cells. Potently regulates cellular-mediated immunity and directs cytotoxic T lymphocytes and NK cell effector activity in the clearance of tumours.	IL-13	Inhibits inflammatory cytokine production. Induces immunoglobulin E secretion from B-lymphocytes.

Introduction to the herpes family

The human herpes virus (HHV) family consist of 9 members, with the generic name HHV- followed by a number and occasionally a letter. The viruses all have an acute phase where there are symptoms of disease and the virus is active or lytic. Once the lytic phase has finished the viruses adopt a dormant or latent phase in the nucleus of different cells in the body, during which time the virus does not replicate or cause disease. Under certain circumstances the viruses can be stimulated to switch from the latent states into the lytic state when the person is likely to be infectious or shedding virus but may not have symptoms. Table 2 lists the different herpes viruses alongside their more familiar names, the diseases they cause and the cells where they lie latent, although these may not be the cells that are initially infected, table 3 lists the common name and the syndromes associated with infection of the lytic virus and table 4 lists conditions that some authors have associated with herpes virus infection, although no investigation into the veracity of the evidence has been undertaken.

Group	Virus Name	Primary targets of infection	Site of Latency
Alphaherpesviruses	HHV-1	Epithelial cells	Trigeminal ganglia
	HHV-2	Epithelial cells	Sacral ganglia Neurons
	HHV-3	Epithelial cells	Trigeminal and dorsal root ganglia
Betaherpesviruses	HHV-5	Endothelial cells in different tissues	Monocytes or granulocyte-macrophage progenitors
	HHV-6a	CD4+ T cells	T-cells and macrophages, salivary glands, central nervous system
	HHV-6b	CD4+ T cells	T-cells and macrophages, salivary glands, central nervous system
	HHV-7	CD4+ T cells	Brain, salivary glands, gastric mucosa
Gammaherpesviruses	HHV-4	B cells and oropharyngeal epithelium	B and T cells
	HHV-8		Brain and lymphocytes

Table 2: Herpes Virus Family(Ng 2002)

Virus Name	Common Name	Syndrome	Prevalence (%)
HHV-1	Herpes Simplex	Oral herpes (cold sores), encephalitis, erythema multiforme pharyngitis	52-85%
HHV-2	Herpes Simplex	Genital herpes	22%
HHV-3	Varicella Zoster	Chicken Pox/Shingles	99%
HHV-4	Epstein Barr Virus	Glandular fever/Infectious mononucleosis, severe mosquito bite allergy drug-induced hypersensitivity syndrome	90%
HHV-5	Cytomegalovirus	Glandular fever/Infectious mononucleosis retinitis drug-induced hypersensitivity syndrome	83%
HHV-6a	Roseolovirus	roseola infantum or sixth disease, Kawasaki disease, drug-induced hypersensitivity syndrome	95%
HHV-6b	Roseolovirus	roseola infantum or sixth disease	95%
HHV-7	Roseolovirus	drug-induced hypersensitivity syndrome, encephalopathy, hemiconvulsion-hemiplegia-epilepsy syndrome, hepatitis infection, postinfectious myeloradiculoneuropathy, pityriasis rosea	85%
HHV-8	Kaposi's sarcoma-associated herpesvirus	Kaposi's sarcoma	Varies between geographical regions between 3.7%(Spain) and 46% (Nigeria)

Table 3: association of virus and syndromes

System	Condition	Implicated pathogens	Reference
Nervous system	Bell's Palsy	HHV1, HHV3, HHV4, HHV5, HHV6	Genizi et al (2019), Grose et al 1973, Grose et al 1975, Vahine et al 1981
	Guillain-Barre Syndrome	HHV3, HHV4, HHV5	Corssmit et al 1997, Grose et al 1972, Jacobs et al 1997; Leung et al 2020; Ormerod, Cockerell 1993; Yuki et al 2001; Susuki et al 2009; Kang et al 2010
	Transverse Myelitis	HHV1, HHV4, HHV5, HHV6	Arsian et al 2015, Caldas et al 1994, Karacostas et al 2002, Poorthuis et al 2018, Rigamonti et al 2019, Giobbia et al 1999
	Encephalitis	HHV4, HHV5, HHV6, HHV7	Arribas et al 1996, Asano et al 1992, Doja et al 2006, Ishiguro et al 1990, Ongrádiet al 2017, Corssmit et al 1997
	Multiple Sclerosis	HHV4, HHV5	Levin et al 2010; Ascherio et al 2010.; Serafiniet al 2007; Pumphrey et al 2022; Bjornevik et al 2022
Cardiovascular	Pericarditis/myocarditis	HHV2, HHV4, HHV5, HHV6	Chimenti et al 2020; Colombo et al 2022; Hebbert et al 1995; Ishikawa et al 2005; Koga et al 2001; Maisch et al 1985; Reddy et al 2015
	Atherosclerosis	HHV4, HHV5	Grivel et al 2013, Kaklikkaya et al 2010, Kotronias et al 2005, Streblow et al 2001, Nikitskaya et al 2016, Morre et al 2000, Ibrahim et al 2005, Shi et al 2002, Al-Ghamdi 2012, Benditt et al 1983, Jarrett et al 1996, Degre 2002, Epstein et al 1996, Sorlie et al 2000
Haematological	Haemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis	HHV4, HHV5	Marsh(2018), Zimmer et al(2021), Kikuta (1995)
	clotting disorders	HHV4, HHV5	Wu et al 2013; Kagoya et al 2010; van Steijn et al 2000; Bader et al 2010; Niewold et al 2006; Müller et al 2015; Goeijenbier et al 2012; Cooper & Busse 2006; Rinaldi et al 2014
Obs/Gynae	Pregnancy associated problems	HHV-5	Aurita et al 2021; Yamamoto et al 2001; Shi et al 2018
Multiple Systems	Cancer	HHV4, HHV5, HHV7, HHV8	Ahmed et al 2012, Chen et al 2015, Shinozaki-Ushiku et al 2015, Hong et al 2015, Eliassen et al 2018, Grywalska et al 2015, Ferry et al 2009, Michaelis et al 2009, Mygatt et al 2013, Ursu et al 2021, 55, 56, 57, 58
	DRESS	HHV6, HHV7	Drago et al 2016; Ichiche et al 2003; Ogawa et al 2014

Table 4: Conditions where HHV family may be involved

Cytokines in acute herpes virus infections

It is relevant to consider the cytokine profile of an initial acute infection from HHV4 which causes infectious mononucleosis (IM a B cell infection) and haemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (HLH a CD 8+ T cell infection) in children.

A study of 22 children was performed to determine whether there was a link between cytokine profile and the cell type that was infected. The cytokine profiles, which represent an antiviral Th1 response, are summarised in the table below.

Cytokine	IM cohort (n=11)	HLH cohort (n=11)
IFN- γ	+	++
IL-6	+	++
IL-18	+	++
TNF- α	+ (5/11) / ++ (6/11)	++

The authors are at pains to point out that the cytokine profile of the HLH is not dissimilar to the profile of children with familial haemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis due to perforin deficiency suggesting that the observed profile in the HLH cohort is likely to be a consequence of HLH rather than the result of the proliferation of infected CD8+ T cells. (Wada et al 2013). It is worth noting that in both situations the cytokine profile is consistent with a strong Th1 response as would be expected in an acute infection.

Reactivation of Herpes viruses

As noted earlier, herpes viruses remain in their target cells for the hosts lifetime in their latent state, however that is not guaranteed and the state can switch from latency to active infection if certain conditions develop. The exact mechanism for reactivation is poorly understood but there appear to be factors that trigger the change of state.

One such external factor that has been implicated in the reactivation of HHV-1, HHV-3, HHV-4 is stress (Padgett et al 1998, Mehta et al 2004, Glaser et al 1991), with Dhabar (2009) suggesting that the stress response has an impact on the immune system, with acute stress, lasting for periods of minutes or hours, and chronic stress, lasting from a few hours to weeks or even months, enhancing or diminishing the immune response respectively.

Elenkov and Chrousos (2002) suggest that the major stress hormones, glucocorticoids and catecholamines, inhibit the production of IL-12, TNF- α and IFN- γ (Th-1 cytokines) whilst stimulating the production of IL-10, IL-4 and TGF- β (Th-2 cytokines), thus changing from a Th-1 immune response to a Th-2 response.

There are three types of immune response suggested, immunoprotection, Immunopathology and immunosuppression, the former having a beneficial impact on health whilst the latter two having a negative impact on health.

Acute stress, it is suggested is beneficial (immunoprotection), unless there is autoimmunity or exposure to allergens when it can be harmful (immunopathology). Whereas chronic stress is associated with harm, although if the stress causes immunosuppression then there is a beneficial aspect in the reduction of inflammation and autoimmune disease (Dhabar 2009).

One area where there has been extensive research is the effect of stresses associated with space travel and the subsequent reactivation of different herpes viruses (Mehta & Pierson 2008, Mehta et al 2013, Mehta et al 2014, Crucian et al 2015, Mehta et al 2017, Rooney et al 2019)

Mehta et al (2013) compared cytokine levels between 17 test subjects who made space flights lasting between nine and fourteen days and 10 control subjects who remained on Earth.

Saliva samples were collected from each astronaut before, during and after spaceflight. The pre-flight samples were collected on alternate days for a month some three months prior to launch day. Daily samples were collected during the mission. Post mission samples were collected on landing day and then daily for 15 days and finally one sample 120 days post landing. The control group had samples collected on alternate days for four weeks.

Urine samples were collected from the test subjects ten days prior to launch, two hours post landing and 3 days post landing. Three urine samples from each of the control group were included. Finally, blood samples were taken from the test subjects 10 days pre-launch, then after two hours, three days and 120 days post landing. The control group had blood taken on day 0, day 22 and day 25, corresponding to 10 days prior to the launch of a simulated space mission lasting 12 days, the day of landing and three days post landing.

The samples obtained were tested for the presence of HHV-3, HHV-4 and HHV-5.

Of the seventeen test subjects the presence of one or more of the viruses was detected in the urine or saliva samples collected during or post mission of nine who were designated shedders, the remaining eight astronauts plus the control group were designated non-shedders.

The cytokines analysed were the inflammatory IL-1 α , IL-1 β , TNF α , IL-6 and IL-8; the lymphoid growth factors IL-2, IL-7 and IL-15; the Th1/17 cytokines IFN γ , IL-12, IL-17; Th2 cytokines IL-4, IL-5, IL-10 and IL-13; myeloid growth factors G-CSF and GM-CSF; the chemokines Eotaxin, MCP-1, MIP1a and IP-10.

120 days after landing the levels in the test group were comparable with the control group, therefore these were used as the baseline.

The comparison between virus shedders and non-shedders is summarised below:

Cytokine (Th type)	Virus Shedders	Non Shedders
IL-1 α (Th1)	+	-
IL-4 (Th2)	++++	+
IL-6 (Th1)	++++	-
IL-8	+	-
IL-10 (Th2)	+	-
IL-12 (Th1)	+	-
IL-13 (Th2)	+	-
IFN γ (Th1)	++	-
IP-10	+	+
Eotaxin	+	-

Cytokine levels

It is concluded that viral reactivation appears to be connected to a shift towards Th-2 cytokine balance (Mehta et al 2012).

In a later study of astronauts spending longer periods of time in space, between 60 and 180 days in the International Space Station (ISS). It has previously been assumed that people would become acclimatised after spending long periods in the space environment, however, this study shows that the immune system remains compromised with an increase in the reactivation of HHV-3, HHV-4 & HHV-5, with 22 out of 23 test subjects shedding one or more of the three target viruses. Plasma cortisol levels were found to decrease during the mission taking around 30 days to recover to pre-flight levels. (Mehta et al 2014)

Crucian et al (2015) noted changes in the adaptive immune system during a 6 month mission in the ISS which included reductions in the levels of the Th1 cytokines TNF α , IFN γ , IL-6 and the Th2 cytokines IL-10, IL-5, an increase in the levels of IL-8, a chemokine

that attracts neutrophils, basophils and T cells during the inflammatory phase of the innate immune response, and a reduction in the number of CD4+ T cells capable of producing the Th1 cytokine IL-2 on landing. Altemus (2001) also notes that IL-10, a Th-2 cytokine, increases in times of acute stress.

Another area that has been extensively studied is the reactivation of various human herpesviruses in patients who are in intensive care/therapy units (ICU/ITU).³³⁻⁴⁷

This is within the context of other infections contracted by ITU patients, data from 15,202 patients in 1150 centres across 88 countries was gathered for 24 hours on the 13th September 2017. Infection data was obtained for 15,165 (99.8%). Across all units 10,640 (70%) were being treated with at least one antibiotic; 8,135 (54%) patients had infection which was either proven or suspected, of which 1,760 were infections acquired within the ITU. The overall mortality rate amongst patients with infections was 30%. (Vincent et al 2020)

In a study of patients admitted to ITU over a five year period, 60 autopsies and 26 open lung biopsies were performed on patients with signs/symptoms of acute respiratory failure or suggestive of cytomegalovirus (HHV5) pneumonia. Ventilator associated HHV5 pneumonia was diagnosed by cytological assay in 25 patients between 10 and 40 days (median 18 days) post admission. The clinical description for the 25 ventilated patients was similar to the 61 non-ventilated patients; however, there was a striking difference in the levels of hypoxaemia between the two cohorts with the non-ventilated cohort having 95 +/- 41 mm mercury compared with 72 +/- 16 mm mercury for the ventilated cohort⁴¹

It is suggested that corticosteroids may be beneficial in patients with fibrosis associated with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), however there is no method to differentiate between a fibrotic stage and nosocomial pneumonia.

The study by Papazian et al (1998) was to determine the efficacy and safety of performing open lung biopsies on patients with persistent ARDS who were ventilated but without bacterial involvement. 36 patients out of 197 patients on ventilators with acute respiratory distress syndrome were examined with open lung biopsies. 41% (15/36) were found to have fibrosis, of these only 6 were treated with corticosteroids as the remaining 9 were found to have HHV5 pneumonia, a contraindication for steroid therapy. In total 18 patients were HHV5 positive by histological assay, of the 9/18 who had lung tissue cultured for HHV5 four were found to be positive. The authors do caution that it is difficult to determine whether HHV5 infection precedes ARDS or vice versa without further study.

In a metastudy Osawa and Singh (2009) suggest that up to 36% of ICU patients develop HHV5 infection within 4 to 12 days of admission. Risk factors for developing HHV5 infection include sepsis, mechanical ventilation and transfusion with associated risk factors of sepsis. Such infection is associated with poor outcomes for the patient.

Herpes Simplex Virus (HHV1) has also been found in the secretions of ventilated patients, with Bruynseels et al (2003) reporting that HHV1 was detected in oropharyngeal swabs of 169 of 729 patients admitted to ITU, of the 169 patients this occurred within 10 days of admission for 150 (89%) patients. The virus was isolated from the lower respiratory tract in 58 out of 361 patients who were tested. Suggesting that the presence of HHV1 in the throat is a risk factor for development of infection in the lower respiratory tract and its associated risks of developing ARDS and an extended stay in ITU. However, Simmoons-Smit et al (2006) argue that a clear diagnosis of pneumonia caused by HHV1 is difficult as there are no specific clinical criteria; that there are no specific risk factors neither is there consistent data on the efficacy of antivirals. It is suggested that further studies are required to define the pathogenesis, improve diagnostic techniques and the necessity of anti-viral treatment in individual patients.

Luyt et al (2007) identified 42 out of 201 (21%) deteriorating ventilated patients diagnosed with HHV1 related bronchopneumonitis 14 +/- 6 days after mechanical ventilation was commenced. It is suggested that this may be related to infection or reactivation of HHV1 in the oropharyngeal cavity and is associated with poorer outcome.

In a study of 90 people who were patients in ITU for 5 or more days, samples of blood or obtained from bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) were tested for the presence of DNA from HHV1, HHV4, HHV5. HHV4 was detected in the blood of 61 patients; HHV5 in the blood of 16 patients and in the BAL of a further 6; HHV1 in the BAL of 28 patients. 19 patients had no evidence of reactivation. Of those who had evidence of reactivation, 1 had solely HHV5, 32 had solely HHV4 and 5 had solely HHV1. Of the remainder 6 had evidence of both HHV4 and HHV5, 14 had HHV4 and HHV1 with the remaining 9 having evidence of all three viruses being reactivated. (Libert et al 2015)

80 intensive care patients who met the inclusion criteria of being ventilated, immunocompetent, with active Immunoglobulin G (IgG) against HHV5 and were aged 18+ in the intensive therapy unit (ITU) in one of two Greek hospitals between 2010 and 2012 were incorporated into a study. On admission to the ITU plasma levels of interferon (IFN) γ , interleukin (IL) 10, IL-17A, IL-2, IL-6, and tumour necrosis factor (TNF) α were measured along with morning saliva levels of cortisol.

With reactivation being defined as the presence of 500 or more copies of HHV5 DNA per ml of plasma. It was found that 11/80 patients to have evidence of HHV5 reactivation with higher levels of IL-10 and IL-6 compared with the 69 who had no evidence of reactivation. Whilst the levels of TNF α , IFN γ and IL-17A showed no statistically difference between the two groups. (Frantzeskaki et al 2015)

Further evidence of the reactivation of herpes viruses in patients with severe ARDS is provided by Hraiech et al (2019) who identified 123 patients over a five year period

requiring extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO), of these 67 patients were found to have reactivation of HHV1 or HHV5. 40 had HHV1, 7 had HHV5 and 20 had both HHV1 and HHV5.

Infections and reactivation of herpes viruses

Ventilator associated pneumonia(VAP) appears to be the significant risk factor in mortality for CoViD19 patients with staphylococcus aureus and pseudomonas being the predominant bacterial causes, although other bacterial and fungal causes have been identified (Maes et al 2021, Giacobbe et al 2021, Boyd et al 2022).

Maes et al (2021) suggest that the risk of developing VAP is approximately double in patients with CoViD19 compared with non-CoViD19 patients. Although they consider the presence of herpes viruses to be due to reactivation rather than being pathogenic in the development of VAP, they did test for HHV1, HHV4 and HHV5 in patients with CoViD19 and those without. 10 out of 24 patients with CoViD19 were positive for the presence of one or more herpes viruses compared with 5 out of 25 patients without CoViD19. In contrast, other authors would argue that the presence of herpes viruses is pathogenic and has a detrimental effect on mortality (Bruynseels (2003), Luyt et al (2007). Libert et al (2015), Hraiech et al (2019), Meyer et al (2021)). The ratio of covid patients to non covid patients with VAP is similar to the ratio of covid patients to non covid patients with evidence of herpes virus, Maes et al(2021), whether this a coincidental or a causal relationship warrants further investigation.

Reactivation of HHV3 has also been associated with SARS-CoV-2 infection (Siddiqui, Hasnain 2022) which may be due to immunosuppressive mechanisms, as yet unidentified, however as previous studies appear to demonstrate that reactivation is associated with a shift from Th1 to Th2, then this could be an explanation (Mehta et al 2012).

Reactivation of HHV8 associated with SARS-CoV-2 proteins and drugs used to treat CoViD19 has been observed in an in vitro study. Specifically, with the addition of doxycycline it was reported that there was a significant increase in the reactivation of HHV8 in cells infected with the spike protein or the nucleotide protein compared to the number of reactivations in similarly infected cells without doxycycline. Similar reactivation was seen with the addition of the antibiotic azithromycin or the synthetic serine protease inhibitor nafamostat mesylate. (Chen et al 2021).

García-Martínez et al (2020) report of a 19 year old patient with a two day history of fever, hemifacial swelling, lymphadenopathy, tonsillitis and splenomegaly. Tests revealed the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in the mucosa of the mouth and throat, with both IgM and IgG antibodies to HHV4, measles and mumps. However the mumps virus was not detected in a saliva cell culture, and the diagnosis was infectious mononucleosis and asymptomatic COVID19. The authors were unable to rule out involvement of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and cautioned against assuming that every presentation with pyrexia is SARS-CoV-2/CoViD19, particularly if such presentations have never manifested themselves before.

The reactivation of herpes viruses has been suggested as a factor in the development of post acute CoViD19 sequelae (PACS), colloquially known as long covid, with Söderberg-Nauclé (2021) suggesting that the reactivation of HHV5 and an associated immune dysfunction may be being underestimated in development of severe covid19. It is further suggested that in some patients, reactivation of HHV5 may be responsible for an ongoing inflammatory response after SARS-CoV-2 is no longer detectable, thus being relevant for long covid patients. This thread was picked up by Peluso and Geeks (2022) who suggest that the reactivation of HHV4 during acute illness is one factor that is implicated in the development of PACS.

In a study of 61 CoViD19 patients, 11 were found to have viraemia for HHV4 (9) or HHV5 (2). Although those with HHV4 viraemia were at a higher risk of developing severe disease, this was deemed to be statistically insignificant; however of the two with HHV5 viraemia, one unfortunately died whilst the other survived after use of Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation (ECMO). (Im et al 2020).

In a study of 34 patients admitted into ITU with a confirmed CoViD19 diagnosis were tested for the presence of HHV-4, HHV-5 or HHV-6 DNA in blood samples. HHV-4 was found in 82% (28/34); HHV-5 in 15% (5/34) and HHV-6 in 22% (7/34). Reactivation of HHV-4 was seen soon after ITU admission and was associated with longer length of stay in ITU. (Simonnet et al 2021).

It is suggested that when HHV4 reactivates it causes an increase in the number of ACE2 receptors expressed on epithelial cell membranes, thus potentially increasing susceptibility to infection of epithelial cells by SARS-CoV-2. This suggests that treating patients with antivirals to prevent the replication of HHV4 may reduce SARS-CoV-2 susceptibility. (Verma et al 2021)

Drug reactions and reactivation of herpes viruses

The immediate concern following the administration of any medication is the development of allergic reaction, particularly anaphylaxis which can be fatal if not recognised promptly. As the formulation for the covid19 vaccines varies depending on both the manufacturer and the delivery mechanism. Both Pfizer and Moderna formulations use nanolipids to carry the mRNA, of these only polyethylene glycol (PEG) has been identified as a potential allergen, other ingredients in the Moderna formulation are potential allergens but remain unidentified as such. The AstraZeneca vaccines has one potential allergen, polysorbate 80. (Rutkowski et al 2021)

The possibility that herpes viruses could be reactivated by vaccinations was considered in a paper that reported three individuals who developed HHV3 after having three different vaccinations. It was noted, however, that this could be coincidental, whilst emphasising that immunomodulation has been observed following vaccinations for pneumococcal (immunosuppressive), hepatitis B (reduction in alloreactivity) and killed measles virus (suppression of cell mediated immunity). It is suggested that in these three cases there could be immunomodulation precipitated by the vaccine but that further epidemiological study is required (Walter et al 1999).

A more serious reaction to medication in general is Drug Induced Hypersensitivity Syndrome (DIHS) also referred to as Drug Reaction with Eosinophilia and Systemic Symptoms (DRESS). Drugs known to be associated with DIHS include antibiotics, antivirals and anticonvulsants. Seven patients (2 male, 5 female) aged 19-84 years of age were seen in hospital 3 to 16 days after onset of symptoms of drug induced hypersensitivity syndrome (DIHS). The symptoms including fever and skin eruptions occurred between 21 and 47 days after the first dose of the medication. Serum PCR tests for HHV4, HHV5, HHV6 and HHV7 were completed on admission, additionally qPCR tests

were run on sera of two of the patients. Peripheral blood tests indicated raised leukocytes, raised eosinophils and atypical lymphocytes were found in all 7 patients. HHV4 DNA was identified in two patients on days 36 and 44 post onset of symptoms; HHV5 DNA was detected in all seven patients between 32 and 51 days post onset; HHV6 DNA and HHV7 DNA was detected in all 7 patients between days 21 and 35 post onset. It may be significant to note that in all cases of HHV4 and HHV5 DNA being identified a positive result for HHV6/HHV7 DNA always preceded it, although no explanation for this observation was forthcoming (Seishima et al 2006).

Schroeder et al (2022) discuss a case of a 47 year old male with a history of ulcerative colitis and asthma presenting at an emergency department in Italy with a seven day history of fever persistent cough, headache and itchy rash. The symptoms developed after the second dose of the Pfizer mRNA vaccine, which had been administered three weeks after the primary dose. The first symptoms, myalgia, abdominal and chest pain associated with productive cough occurred shortly after the vaccination, with the fever, productive cough and rash developing 5 days later. The patient had a history of angioedema after aspirin, with no other drug allergies. Blood tests revealed raised eosinophils but was negative for HHV-4, HHV-5, HHV-6 and HHV-8, thus the patient was diagnosed with DRESS, which occurs 3-8 weeks after the first dose of the drug responsible.

Griffin et al (2020) present the case of DRESS in an 81 year old patient, that was precipitated atypically by an influenza vaccination seven days earlier. The presence of HHV-1, HHV-3 and HHV-5 was tested for and found to be negative, however no explicit test for HHV-6 was done, and, although not explicitly mentioned it appears the HHV-4 was not tested for either. None of the patients regular medications have been implicated in the development of DRESS, which prompts the authors to hypothesise that the cause may

have been a component of the vaccine, although a possible role for the reactivation of herpes viruses is not excluded.

O'Connor et al (2021) present the case of a 45 year old presenting with symptoms of DRESS some seven weeks after receiving the AstraZeneca adenovirus based CoVID19 vaccine. Whilst Lospinosa et al (2021) report on a similar case of DRESS following the Janssen adenovirus based vaccine

Walter et al (2000) report on a 13 year old female allogenic haemopoietic progenitors transplant recipient. Two years post transplant she had a complete childhood vaccination programme and developed HHV3 after every dose. It is hypothesised that vaccine-induced immunomodulation was the cause of the reactivation.

More recently, Psychogiou et al (2021) report on seven patients who developed HHV-3 between one and three weeks post vaccination against SARS-CoV-2, with a mean of 9 days.

In a literature review of 12 papers which reported on 91 patients who presented with reactivation of HHV-3 following SARS-CoV-2 vaccination. Twelve of the ninety-one had an autoimmune condition, with rheumatoid arthritis being the most common. Nine were receiving immunosuppressive medication. Fourteen patients had a previous history of HHV-3 and twelve had been vaccinated against HHV-3. Of this group, seven patients had had no previous reactivation and eleven were not vaccinated against HHV-3. Altogether 7 patients out of 91 had a previous history of SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Most of the participants (53/91) developed symptoms after the first dose, whilst 35/91 it was after the second dose, two of the remaining studies did not state when the symptoms appeared and one study symptoms developed in all participants after the first dose. The average time for symptom onset within each study ranged from 3.6 days to 9 days post vaccination, giving an average time across all of the studies of 5.8 days independent of the

dose administered. The shortest average onset time was reported from Taiwan, with the longest being reported in the Greek study. (Katsikas Triantafyllidis et al 2021)

Fathy et al (2022) in their correspondence report that as of April 2021, over 650 cases of skin reactions that appear to have been associated with the SARS-CoV-2 vaccine were recorded in the International Dermatology Register. The first forty cases listed as being HHV1 or HHV3 that were associated with either of the mRNA vaccines (Pfizer or Moderna) were subject to further review. Of these 40, 35 cases were of HHV-3 reactivation with the remainder being HHV-1 reactivation. Of the 35 HHV-3 reactivation cases, 19 had been given the Pfizer vaccine and 16 the Moderna. 77% of the cases occurred after the first dose only, with no reported flare ups after the second dose. The reported onset ranged from 2 days to 13 days post vaccination, giving a mean of 7 days.

The authors do identify some limitations with the study in that there is no record in the registry as to how HHV-1/HHV-3 was diagnosed, whether PCR or by clinical signs. Also there is no record of any immunocompromised conditions or HHV3 vaccination or immune status, finally there is no unvaccinated control group. However, they do mention that other vaccinations such as Hepatitis A and influenza have had HHV-3 reactivation associated with them. As reactivation appears to be related to both the Pfizer and the Moderna and in approximately the same proportions, it is suggested that the immune response to mRNA may be responsible, although the exact mechanism is unknown. The authors suggest that these reactivations may be due to immune system failures initiated by the host response to the vaccination (Fathy et al 2022).

Meng et al (2022) reviewed 1314 patients admitted to a hospital in Wuhan by 12th March 2020, of these 1097 patients were excluded as there were no serology results for identified reactivation of Epstein-Barr Virus (HHV-4) or Cytomegalovirus (HHV-5), leaving 217

patients, of whom 30 unfortunately died with the remaining 187 being discharged. Of the 217 patients, 55 were found to have evidence of reactivation of HHV-4.

Laboratory results for those with HHV-4 reactivation compared with those with no HHV-4 reactivation are summarised in the table below:

Parameter		Expected range	No HHV-4 reactivation	HHV-4 Reactivation
Hb	Female	115-165	129	122
	Male	130-180		
D-dimer		< 0.5	0.56	0.9
Total Bilirubin		< 21	10.95	12.5
ALT	Female	<33	30.5	27
	Male	<41		
AST		1-45	32	35
IL-6		< 5.9	7.48	8.01

Notes: a) the referenced paper does not differentiate between male and female blood results.

b) IL-6 reference range obtained from <https://ourhealthtip.com/interleukin-6-laboratory-test-ranges-reference/>

The IL-6 levels in this study appear to be similar to the levels found in the astronauts who were found to be shedding HHV-4 (Mehta et al 2013). However as no other cytokines were measured in the study by Meng et al (2022), there is little evidence of a shift from Th1 to Th2 , as suggested by Mehta et al (2013), particularly in those who showed signs of reactivation of HHV-4.

Agrawal et al (2022) report on ten patients who developed evidence of reactivation of HHV-3 between 4 and 21 days post vaccination, with symptoms appearing between 4 days and 21 days post vaccination, 8 developed symptoms after the first dose and 2 after the second.

Of the eight (8/10) who experienced symptoms after the first dose 2 developed symptoms 4 days post vaccination; 1 after five days; 1 after 7 days; 1 after eight days; 1 after 9 days; 1 after 10 days; 1 after 14 days. Of the two (2/10) that developed symptoms after the second dose 1 was after 8 days and the other was after 21 days.

Daouk et al (2022) report on the case of a 12 year old child who developed severe abdominal pain 11 days post vaccination with the Pfizer mRNA vaccine. Subsequently he developed headache, photophobia and twitching movements with HHV-3 being detected in the child's cerebrospinal fluid. Following treatment for ten days with intravenous acyclovir he was discharged with no apparent problems. It is hypothesised that the CoViD19 vaccination caused a shift in CD8+ T cell immunity, although this requires further investigation.

A 24 year old male presented with a non itching rash to his torso that had started on his arm three weeks post vaccination against covid19. Titres for antibodies against HHV5, HHV6, HHV7, HHV3, hepatitis A, coxsackie viruses were all negative or indicative of past immunity. However, serology for HHV4 was positive for IgM antibodies against the viral capsid antigen and IgG antibodies against the viral nuclear antigen, suggestive of a reactivation of the virus. (Herzum et al 2022).

With the report that the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 is implicated in the reactivation of HHV8, then given that the mRNA and the adenovirus vector vaccines both cause the creation of spike protein then there is a chance that they could also reactivate HHV8 in some people. The reactivation of HHV8 could trigger Kaposi's sarcoma in immunocompromised patients or people with genetic susceptibility and should be monitored for.(Chen et al 2021).

In a more recent paper (Navarro-Bielsa et al 2023) report on the number of herpes virus infections that have been recorded as suspected adverse drug reactions following vaccination with the four main covid19 vaccines. Across all herpes viruses there are a total of almost 25000 cases, of which almost 20000 are associated with the Pfizer, the totals are summarised in the table below (Note that there may be an error in the data in the original paper).

Vaccine	Number of herpes infections
Moderna	1531
Pfizer/Biontech	19889
AstraZeneca	3307
Janssen	222
Total	24831

Discussion and recommendations

Evidence suggests that the various herpes viruses are reactivated if there is a shift from the Th1 immune response towards the Th2 response as demonstrated in the changes in cytokines identified in astronauts (Mehta et al 2012). Furthermore herpes reactivation has been noted in patients who also have parasitic infection with helminths, which are recognised as inducing a shift to a Th2 response through the generation of IL-4 which blocks the antiviral effects of IFN γ thus allowing viral replication (Reese et al 2014).

Interestingly, acute infection by HHV4 rather than reactivation appears to prevent a humoral response to the malaria parasite (Matar et al 2015).

Although the details of the reactivation of HHV are poorly understood, Siddiqui & Hasnain (2021) postulate that because SARS-CoV-2 infection can result in a hyperinflammatory state (Merad & Martin 2020) which leads to dysregulation of the immune system and ultimately reactivation of HHV-3. Merad & Martin (2020) identify the presence of IL-6, IL-7 and TNF- α in patients in the hyperinflammatory state which is suggestive of activation of the mononuclear phagocyte compartment that is dysregulated. Interestingly, reactivation of HHV in those astronauts who were actively shedding virus was also marked by a significant increase in IL-6 levels in addition to the increase in Th2 cytokines (Mehta et al 2012); similarly for in patients in ITU (Meng et al 2022, Frantzeskaki et al 2015). Noisakran et al (1998), noted increased levels of IL-6 in mice that resulted in a reactivation of HHV-1; TNF- α is similarly implicated.

The major difference between the papers discussing the reactivation in astronauts is that Th2 cytokines were measured alongside the Th1 cytokines whereas there appears to be no indication that similar tests were done on the subject patients in the later CoViD-19 studies. Thus, it is recommended that tests to establish Th2 cytokine levels are performed in all patients who have signs and symptoms of reactivation of any herpes virus.

The reactivation of different herpes viruses have been associated with both acute SARS-CoV-2 infection and the CoViD19 vaccines, what is not clear is whether signs and symptoms associated with CoViD19 are due solely to SARS-CoV-2 or a combination of SARS-CoV-2 and reactivated herpes viruses, likewise for the more serious adverse events reported for the CoViD19 vaccines. Even if there is clear evidence from blood tests for the presence of reactivated herpes viruses whether these are responsible for any of the symptoms warrants further investigation.(García-Martínez et al 2020, Söderberg-Nauclér 2021). It is recommended that if an adverse effect follows vaccination then other causes should be eliminated first (Halsey et al 2012, Rutkowski et al 2021, Pomara et al 2021). As recent reactivation of HHV4 or HHV5, as evidenced by the presence of antibodies but without viraemia, appears to affect the chances of developing PACS (Peluso et al 2023) or other serious illness (Simonnet et al 2021), it is recommended that tests for pathogens additional to those for SARS-CoV-2/CoViD-19 are carried out. (Aghbash et al 2021). Furthermore, it is recommended that regular testing for herpes viruses is completed on all patients in ITU who are mechanically ventilated and possibly for patients on bi-level positive airway pressure (BIPAP) or continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP).

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Appendix
Summary tables

Observed herpes infections associated with SARS-COV-2 infection

Reference	Study/Report	Results
Ferreira et al (2020)	HHV 3	39 year old male developed left sided facial shingles concurrent with CoViD-19
García-Martínez et al (2020)	HHV 4	19 year old female with positive PCR test for SARS-CoV-2 and HHV 4
Nofal et al (2020)	HHV 3 infection of eyes	4 patients, age range 7-42 years of age, 3 male and 1 female developed eye pathology 4 or 5 days post CoViD-19 symptom onset
Pona et al (2020)	HHV 3	70 year old female with hypertension and complicated diabetes mellitus developed ipsilateral hip rash several days after developing CoViD-19
Saati et al (2020)	HHV 3	57 year old male developed ipsilateral rash four days after developing symptoms of CoViD-19
Siddiqui, Hasnain (2020)	HHV 3 observed during or after SARS-CoV-2 infection	
Abadias-Granado et al (2021)	HHV 6	12/53 HHV 6 positive
Cabrera Muras et al (2021)	HHV 4	20 year old male with bilateral facial nerve palsy concomitant with SARS-CoV-2 and HHV 4 infections
Chen et al (2021)	HHV 8	
Drago et al (2021)	HHV4, HHV6, HHV7	Single case of pityriasis rosea with positive serology for HHV4, HHV6 and HHV7
Maes et al (2021)	Presence of HHV1, HHV4, HHV5 in covid (n=24) and non covid patients(n=25)	10/24 tested positive in covid cohort 5/25 in non-covid cohort
Paolucci et al (2021)	HHV 4	EBV DNA 40/ 42 (95.2%) of ICU patients and in 51/61 (83.6%) of high dependency unit (HDU) patients. A significant reduction of CD8 T cell and NK count, with increased B cell count in ICU patients compared with HDU patients.
Brooks et al (2022)	HHV 4, HHV 6	15/67 patients HHV 4 positive; 3/67 HHV 6 positive
Ertugrul, G. & Aktas, H. (2022)	Increase in numbers of HHV 3 during SARS-CoV-2	
Elsaie & Nada (2022)	HHV 3	44 year old male developing HHV 3 reactivation concurrent with CoViD-19

Observed herpes infection post vaccination

Reference	Study	Summary
Chiu et al (2021)	HHV3	1 case of HHV3 reactivation (Moderna) 2 cases of HHV3 reactivation (AstraZeneca)
Cyrenne et al (2021)	HHV6	2 cases of Pityriasis rosea like eruptions (Pfizer)
Katsikas Triantafyllidis, et al (2021)	HHV3	Review of literature
Richardson-May et al (2021)	HHV1	1 case of reactivation of HHV1 keratitis (AstraZeneca)
Agrawal et al (2022)	Diagnosis of shingles (HHV3)	10 patients (4 male, 6 female) aged 32-75 years, developed symptoms between 4 and 21 days post vaccination; 8/10 after 1 st dose & 2/10 after 2 nd dose (vaccine not identified)
Fathy et al (2022)	HHV1, HHV3	5 cases of HHV1 reactivation (1 Moderna, 4 Pfizer) 35 cases of HHV3 reactivation (16 Moderna, 19 Pfizer)
Herzum et al (2022)	HHV4	1 case of HHV4 reactivation (Pfizer)